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The first record of the genus *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, 1829 (Coleoptera: Elateridae) in Mongolia

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Abstract. The genus *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, 1829 (Coleoptera: Elateridae) and the species *A. murinus* (Linnaeus, 1758) are recorded for Mongolia for the first time. This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic, mainly in Euro-Siberian region. Two specimens of *A. murinus* were collected in northeastern Mongolia (Töv Province), which is probably the southeasternmost border of the species range.

Key words: Coleoptera, Elateridae, *Agrypnus murinus*, first record, Mongolia.

Первая находка рода *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, 1829 (Coleoptera: Elateridae) в Монголии

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Резюме. Род *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, 1829 (Coleoptera: Elateridae) и вид *A. murinus* (Linnaeus, 1758) впервые указаны для Монголии. Вид широко распространен в Палеарктике, преимущественно в Европе и Сибири. Два экземпляра *A. murinus* были собраны на северо-востоке Монголии (провинция Тове), что, вероятно, является юго-восточной границей ареала этого вида.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Elateridae, *Agrypnus murinus*, первая находка, Монголия.

Introduction

Elateridae is one of the largest families of Coleoptera, which comprises about 10000 species in the world [Lawrence, 1982; Costa et al., 2010]. The fauna of click-beetles of Mongolia includes 38 genera and almost 100 species from eight subfamilies [Jarzabek-Müller, Németh, 2014; Platia, 2017, 2018]. In comparison, fauna of two neighboring countries comprises the following number of taxa: 90 genera and 486 species in Russia, 120 genera and 574 species in China [Ormanova, Yaschenko, 2022]. Accordingly, the click-beetle fauna of Mongolia seems still poorly known and may contain much more species.

Agrypnus Eschscholtz, 1829 is one of the most species-rich elaterid genera (137 species) in the Palaearctic region [Cate, 2007]. In the Palaearctic this genus is most diverse in the mountainous regions of East Asia. Until now, *Agrypnus* was not known in Mongolia, although it is represented in neighboring countries: Russia (four species), Kazakhstan (one species), China (46 species). Here we report the first record of *Agrypnus* for Mongolia.

Study area

Our study area (northeastern Mongolia, Töv Province, Môngönmorit District) is geographically distributed within the Kherlen River watershed, where Baruun Burk Mt. of the Khentii Mountain Range is located. Baruun Burk Mt. is situated at 184 km northeast from Ulaanbaatar (Fig. 1).

The altitude range of the Môngönmorit District is from 1523 to 1897 m above sea level. Mean annual air temperature is -3.7 °C, monthly average air temperature is -27.7 °C in January and $+17$ °C in July. Mean annual precipitation and humidity are around 252 mm and 64%, respectively. The forest types are mesophyte herbaceous, steppe-characterized herbaceous, forest-meadow, Larix and Betula mixed forests [Tsogt, Lin, 2014] (Fig. 2).

Material and methods

The specimens were sampled by manual collecting in 2021. Specimens were collected on the leaves of Betula shrubs in forest edge habitat (Fig. 2), and preserved in 96% ethanol. Images were taken with a Canon EOS 7D Mark II with a Canon 100 mm Macro lens, and processed using Zerene Stacker and Adobe Photoshop CC 2019 software. The material is deposited at the Institute of Biology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences (Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia).

Subfamily Agrypninae Candèze, 1857

Tribe Agrypnini Candèze, 1857

Genus *Agrypnus* Eschscholtz, 1829

Agrypnus murinus (Linnaeus, 1758)

(Figs 3, 4)

Material. 2♂, Mongolia, Töv Prov., Môngönmorit Distr., forest edge with Betula bushes, $48^{\circ}15'37.093''N$ / $108^{\circ}25'24.772''E$, 1582 m, 18.07.2021 (Ts. Ulzii).

Figs 1–4. of *Agrypnus murinus* in northeastern Mongolia, (Möngönmorit District), locality and habitus.

1 – collection site; 2 – habitat; 3–4 – male: 3 – dorsal view, 4 – ventral view.

Рис. 1–4. *Agrypnus murinus* в Северо-Восточной Монголии (район Менгенморьт), местонахождение и внешний вид самца.

1 – место сбора; 2 – биотоп; 3–4 – самец: 3 – дорсально, 4 – вентрально.

Palearctic distribution. Europe (almost all territory) and Asia (Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan; Russia: East Siberia, Far East; China: Xinjiang; Mongolia).

Notes. Two more eastern records of *A. murinus* need confirmation, but seem not so dubious: Zabaykalskiy (around Nerchinsk) [Gebler, 1832] and Khabarovsk [Bessolitzina, 1974] regions, Russia.

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